

Green financial assets: what definition? Introducing a unifying quantitative framework & survey-based definition

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Abstract

This paper introduces for the first time a quantitative framework defining a financial asset’s environmental impact in a manner enabling comparisons across reporting frameworks and academic carbon accounting methods, as well as eliciting public preferences.

A survey representative of the French population shows support for the most comprehensive and recent methodologies. Respondents weigh only slightly less upstream and downstream emissions than Scope 1 emissions. They value a company’s contribution to climate transition scenarios built by public institutions more than carbon offsets. They value biodiversity, water, and chemical pollution more than climate impact in an asset’s impact.

Survey results also support combining academic concepts with more qualitative corporate standards. Value-added environmental accounting could be used instead of Scope 3. Announcements of future emissions should be conditioned on legally binding incentives and governance structures to be counted in a company’s impact. Respondents’ preferences also justify a cumulative accounting of past, present and future estimates, with higher weights for the not too distant future.

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1 Introduction

“At the end of the day, what I think investors need is an end to the alphabet soup and a common language.”

Emmanuel Faber, Chair of the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB)

answering the question ”how will the sustainability disclosure standards take into account the wide variety of existing reporting frameworks and technical standards and the huge variety of jurisdictions?”

This quote illustrates the current plethora of reporting standards for a green company or a green financial asset. These standards can stem from non-profit organizations issuing voluntary reporting standards, labels, regulations or financial data or index providers.

The cost for companies resulting from these multiple reporting requirements calls for standardizing the reporting. But then, which green standard should prevail? Along with this quote, since becoming the head of the ISSB and thus the American regulatory body, Emmanuel Faber criticized the European Union (EU) Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) ¹. He argued that the Europeans should rather adopt the American standards that were under development at that time. Indeed, whoever sets and imposes its standards has preferential access to the more than 2 trillion green investment², possibly lower interest rates ³ for its own ”green activities”, and does not need to readapt and retrain its whole financial industry. These incentives to impose one’s standards also applies at the company level.

This wealth of green standards and the economic incentives to favor one’s preferred investments through one’s own definition could be a cause of the general mistrust surrounding them. Indeed, 59% of French people doubt the sustainability aspect of existing sustainable investments, according to a 2025 study by the French financial regulation agency (AMF). ⁴.

¹Le Monde October 2023 Exiger que la matérialité s’étende au-delà du domaine économique est en réalité simpliste Emmanuel Faber

²<https://www.climatepolicyinitiative.org/publication/global-landscape-of-climate-finance-2025/>

³See the debate regarding a greenium stemming from Bolton and Kacperczyk, 2021

⁴<https://www.amf-france.org/fr/actualites-publications/communiqués/communiqués-de-lamf/finance-durable-les-attentes-des-épargnants-envers-leurs-conseillers-financiers-se-sont-renforcées>

How should we define a green financial asset? How should we define a green firm that could be funded by green investment? What should thus be the definition of a firm and a financial asset's environmental impact, enabling to classify them as green? What is the citizens' opinion? Could providing citizens with more transparency and choice regarding green investment decrease their greenwashing perceptions?

I answer these questions theoretically and empirically. First, I present a quantitative model that defines the environmental impact of a company and then of a financial asset. These environmental impacts are characterized by several dimensions that comprise various variables. Then, 1,959 respondents, representing the French adult population, are asked about their opinion on these variables. Respondents choose how these variables should be accounted for in the environmental impact of a company, and then of green savings products. Only companies and green savings products with a low environmental impact could then be funded by their bank's green savings products.

This paper makes two contributions.

First, it lays out a quantitative model defining the environmental impact of a company and then of a financial asset. This quantitative model enables to model both qualitative criteria used in corporate environmental reporting as well as mathematical formulas defining carbon footprint in academic papers. At the same time, the model enables to rigorously elicit individual investors' preferences on contested criteria. This model enables to compare EU regulations, – the Taxonomy, Sustainable Finance Directive (SFDR), or Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)–, labels – Greenfin –, methodologies from financial and index data providers – such as Trucost, MSCI, Carbon4Finance or 2°Investing –, voluntary reporting frameworks – the Science Based Target Initiative (SBTi), the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), the Task Force on Climate-Related Financial Disclosures (TCFD)–.

Second, this paper shows that respondents' preferences are aligned with the most recent and most comprehensive reporting frameworks, such as the EU CSRD. Respondents value upstream and downstream emissions from a company's value chain, not much less than a company's direct, –i.e Scope 1–, emissions. Respondents value including contributions to climate transition scenarios in a company's environmental impact. They value more climate transition scenarios, – and the resulting emission reduction allocation –, when they are built from public and European institutions, rather than when they represent companies' interests. With these preferred actors building the transition

scenarios, they value these contributions more than climate offsets. Respondents also value more biodiversity, water usage and pollution from chemical or nuclear sources than climate impact. This is consistent with the CSRD reporting requirements on all these impacts and the recent development of methods estimating biodiversity impacts.

Third, according to my model’s estimation respondents’ preferences would support combining academic concepts with existing environmental reporting standards or regulations to define an environmental footprint. Respondents’ underlying preferences agree with value-added carbon accounting (as in Lenzen et al., 2007, Piñero et al., 2019). With this method, a company’s carbon impact equals the emissions from its whole value chain multiplied by the share of its value added over the value added of its whole value chain. This academic method is an alternative to Scope 3. It avoids Scope 3’s multiple counting of emissions when calculating a portfolio’s impact. In the future, value-added accounting could similarly be used for a company’s biodiversity or water impact, as outlined in this paper’s model. Answers also justify a cumulative accounting of past, present and future estimates, with higher weights for the not too distant future.

In the absence of a commitment mechanism, I also suggest estimating future emissions depending on announced emissions, but also on a company’s governance structure and past emission commitments. Respondents support such conditional estimates. They believe that companies with legally binding alternative governance structures or climate-related incentives will emit less in the future.

Literature review

This paper contributes to three literature strands.

First, it contributes to the academic, regulatory, and financial industry debates surrounding the definition of a company or financial asset’s environmental footprint.

It contributes to the academic literature defining the carbon impact of a company or financial asset by modeling additional dimensions stemming from corporate reporting. These dimensions include future estimated emissions, contributions to transition scenarios or accounting for diverse pollution types. Pottier and Le Treut, 2023, Chancel and Rehm, 2023 or Jakob et al., 2021 provide good recent overviews of various methods for calculating the *carbon*

impact of a company or a financial asset. It contributes to the few qualitative comparisons of regulations and corporate reporting. It does so by including academic concepts that could represent alternatives to Scope 3⁵ accounting. It also compares a more diverse set of standards by not focusing only regulatory frameworks. The most comprehensive qualitative comparisons include Ehlers et al., 2021, Marchewitz et al., 2024. This paper’s methodology also contributes to internal methodologies by financial data or index providers. According to interviews, some of these methodologies can rely on quantitative modeling of the different criteria. However, most of these methodologies are not public. The choices made are thus opaque.

Second, this paper extends the political economy literature investigating the support for environmental policies. It examines for the first time country-level preferences regarding the definition of a company or financial asset’s environmental impact. Good recent references are Dechezleprêtre et al., 2022 or Douenne and Fabre, 2020.

Third, this paper adds to the literature investigating preferences regarding green savings products. It does so by carefully disentangling preferences for many criteria sequentially. Several studies are related to this question. Aron-Dine et al., 2024 test the support for green bonds vs. green funds. Bonnefon et al., 2025 test ethical principles behind investment through a lab experiment.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the methodology – methodological choices, survey, data collection, and final sample. Section 3 presents the quantitative model introduced in this paper to define the environmental impact of a company and of a financial asset. Section 4 demonstrates how preferences are substantially aligned with the most recent frameworks defining a firm/asset’s environmental impact and with some academic definitions. Section 5 concludes.

⁵A company’s Scope 3, is a concept developed by the GHG protocol. It consists of all carbon emissions from consumers, companies, and institutions in that company’s value chain and investment relationships.

2 Methodology, survey design & data

2.1 Methodological choices : (expert) preinterviews, population survey

This article makes two main methodological choices. First, it relies extensively on qualitative work and preinterviews, including but not limited to interviews with experts. Second, it surveys a sample representative of the French population.

2.1.1 Surveying the population: a democratic, unbiased method to fight greenwashing perceptions and increase green investment

This project asks a representative sample of the population rather than surveying institutional investors.⁶ There are four reasons for this choice. First, defining green financial products is a democratic question, especially in light of growing public regulations on that subject. This was showcased in debates such as those on the inclusion of the nuclear sector in the EU taxonomy or in the French Livrets A – owned by 85% of French people, and representing most of their financial saving products - . Second, financial institutions have their own investment strategy and corresponding green financial asset definition. Focusing on their answers only, would therefore bias the survey towards favoring their investment strategy. Third, this project investigates whether transparently choosing criteria from the article’s model could decrease citizens’ greenwashing perceptions. Finally, choosing green criteria, and thus reducing greenwashing perceptions could be a lever to increasing green investment. Indeed, individual investors exhibit a high readiness to incur financial losses from green investments as in (Aron-Dine et al., 2024).

2.2 Survey presentation

2.2.1 Survey outline

The different survey parts, the order and wording of questions and answers are all carefully thought out. They are both rigorously consistent with the quantitative model while being understandable by the French population. The order of questions and survey answers is displayed exactly in the same order as their answers appear in Figure 1 and then in Figure3. The only exception is the

⁶It does so after conducting preinterviews with financial sector ESG practitioners and policymakers .

question regarding the preferred actor in charge of developing the transition scenarios. This question is displayed right before the question on the importance of scenario transitions if they are developed by their preferred actors in Figure 1.C.

Respondents have to answer all questions on a given questionnaire page in any order before they can go to the next page. However, once completed, they cannot go back to a previous page. ⁷.

2.3 Data Collection, data quality and final sample

2.3.1 Data collection

The data come from a survey, conducted in September 2025 on 1,959 French adult residents. The survey was designed using the online platform Limesurvey. Participants were enrolled by the commercial survey company Bilendi-Respondi and received survey links via a dashboard and email.

2.3.2 Ensuring data quality

To ensure comprehension by a representative sample of the population and thus data quality, several steps were taken.

First, around 160h of pre-interviews with non -experts uncovered French opinion towards green savings products. This included understanding their green investment behavior, their understanding of green saving products and which environmental impact definitions they could best support. This also enabled to improve the wording of questions. Indeed, pre-interviews showed that some survey questions, if taken directly from related papers, were difficult to understand or ambiguous. Respondents facing a series of such difficult questions would quickly provide answers of a lesser quality or were more likely to abandon the survey ^{8 9}.

⁷The survey link is <https://preferencesfrancais2022.limesurvey.net/961616?newtest=Y&lang=fr>

⁸Semi-directed interviews are also recommended in the quantitative sociology survey literature (Parizot 2012 and Barbot 2012) to prepare the survey

⁹I did not use AI tools at all for help with the wording for two reasons. First, this is an area where AI cannot easily provide references to justify how different categories of people would understand the questions differently or their opinions on this specialized research topic. Second, I considered that understanding people’s opinions, working on bridging the gap between academic questions and people’s concerns or working on widely understandable wording, is part of this study. Social scientists continuing to perform this work mainly through real interactions instead of mostly interacting with Large Language Models, can contribute to sustaining democratic debate.

Second, four test versions of the survey were conducted on a reduced sample before the final survey launch. Between each wave, comprehension tests were conducted and the wording of questions was improved.

Third, to improve data quality, two attention checks to detect and automatically exclude inattentive respondents were included. This is recommended in Stantcheva, 2023.

2.3.3 Final sample characteristics

The final sample of 1959 respondents is close to representative of the French population along many dimensions. This is true by construction for the targeted dimensions of gender, age, urban area size, income and socio-professional category. The final sample is also broadly representative on non-targeted dimensions such as consumption unit, education and financial savings. Importantly, the sample is also representative along the voting patterns of the 2022 presidential election.

The median time for completion of the survey was 26 minutes.

Table 1. SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS: QUOTA STRATAS

	French population	Sample characteristics
Female	.52	.49
Age		
18-24 years old	.12	.03
25-34 years old	.17	.13
35-49 years old	.27	.26
50-64 years old	.23	.37
Over 65 years old	.21	.21
Deciles of household income/consumption unit		
< D2	.20	.22
D2 < ≤ D5	.30	.33
D5 < ≤ D8	.30	.26
> D8	.20	.19
Size of urban area		
Rural (<2k)	.21	.3
2k-19,999	.18	.29
20k-99,999	.14	.2
≥99k outside of Paris area	.30	.15
Paris area	.16	.06
Profession		
Farmer operator	.01	0
Craftsman, merchant, company manager	.06	.03
Managers, liberal profession, higher intellectual profession	.13	.21
Employee	.11	.18
Worker	.19	.08
Intermediate profession, technician	.15	.17
Retired	.30	.24
Other inactive	.05	.08
Sample size		1959

3 Introducing a quantitative model of a company and asset's environmental impact enabling comparisons and testing the support for existing frameworks

I introduce a quantitative model defining the environmental impact of a company and then of a financial asset. This model formalizes the main criteria

used in academic literature, corporate environmental reporting, or green financial indices, facilitating a transparent comparison. At the same time, this model enables to rigorously elicit preferences regarding these criteria through the survey.

This model draws its inspiration from internal methodologies developed by financial indices or data providers to define an asset’s environmental impact.

I first define the environmental impact of a firm f , $\gamma_{t,f}^e$ and then of a financial asset i , γ_i^e and portfolio π , γ_π^e . Time is defined by $t \in \mathbb{Z}$ with the current period being $t = T$.

3.1 A company’s preferred carbon impact in line with the most recent frameworks

In each of this section’s subsections, I test a key dimension describing the macro carbon impact $\gamma_{t,f}$ of a company f a time $t \in \mathbb{Z}$ in methods providing alternatives to the Scope 3. Indeed, the Scope 3 of a company is not precisely defined mathematically and entails multiple counting of portfolio emissions.

3.1.1 What emission’s position in the company’s value chain should we take into account in $\gamma_{t,f}$?

Definitions of a firm f ’s macro carbon impact $\gamma_{t,f}$ can be described by how much they weight f ’s Scope 1 (i.e direct) emissions $\gamma_{t,s_1(f)}$, compared to f ’s $\gamma_{t,u(f)}$ upstream and downstream emissions $\gamma_{t,u(f)}$:

$$\gamma_{t,f} = \omega_{t,u(f)}\gamma_{t,u(f)} + \omega_{t,s_1(f)}\gamma_{t,s_1(f)} + \omega_{t,d(f)}\gamma_{t,d(f)} \quad (1)$$

The Scope 1, upstream and downstream weights, respectively $\omega_{t,s_1(f)}$, $\omega_{t,u(f)}$ and $\omega_{t,d(f)}$ are directly estimated in the survey and shown in Figure 1A.1.

3.1.1.1 How to account for firm f ’s profit share in its value chain in $\gamma_{t,f}$? Definitions of f ’s macro carbon impact $\gamma_{t,f}$ can also be described by whether and how they take into account f ’s profit share $\varsigma(f)$ in f ’s value chain in $\gamma_{t,f}$. If φ is a mapping, with $\varphi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, how does it depend on $\varsigma(f)$?

$$\gamma_{t,f} = \varphi(\varsigma(f)) \quad (2)$$

This question’s answer is shown in Figure 1.A.2.

3.1.2 What carbon emission measures in $\gamma_{t,f}$?

Finally, definitions of a firm f 's macro carbon impact $\gamma_{t,f}$ can be described by the weights $\omega_{t,m,f}$ given to various measures $\gamma_{t,m,f}, m \in \mathcal{M}$ of f 's emission impact. These measures of a firm's emission impacts can include carbon offsets. Indeed, the corresponding emission reduction of a carbon offset, can happen within or outside of a firm's operating scope in most standards. These measures also include a firm's contribution to a transition scenario. Indeed, such a transition scenario depend on the modeling of the whole economy.

$$\gamma_{t,f} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \omega_{t,m,f} \gamma_{t,m,f} \quad (3)$$

These weights are directly estimated in the survey in Figure 1A.3.

Modeling transition scenarios requires making crucial and debatable technical and ethical assumptions. Technical assumptions are needed to use in the model, only the most efficient technologies to reach a society's emission target. Technical assumptions are also needed to model the most efficient order to deploy these technologies. However, sensitive ethical choices are also needed to allocate emission reductions across countries, companies or individuals. Thus, the institution in charge of developing these transition scenarios can make very different choices, based on its own incentives.

Thus, I estimate how much a measure of a firm f 's contribution to a transition scenario $\gamma_{t,st,f}$ should be weighted depending on the origin $o \in \mathcal{O}$ of the scenario.

$$\gamma_{t,f} = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \omega_{t,st(o),f} \gamma_{t,st(o),f} \quad (4)$$

Figure 1 estimates the weights $\omega_{t,st(o),f}$. Each weight corresponds to the percentage of respondents who answered that this institution should develop transition scenarios used in corporate environmental reporting. The underlying ethical debate regarding the allocation of emission reductions was mentioned in the questionnaire. Respondents can choose several institutions that would develop these transition scenarios.

3.2 Estimating a company's *future* $t > T$ carbon Scope 1 emissions $\gamma_{t,s_1}(f)$

The current estimate at time T , of the future Scope 1 carbon emissions of firm f at time $t > T$ is the sum of two elements. The first one, $\bar{\gamma}_{t,s_1}(f)$ are

the *material* future Scope 1 emissions. It is the estimate of the future scope 1 emissions based on material investments or CapEx already realized at time T . $\bar{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)}$ can thus be estimated by specialized consulting firms or experts. The second element $\tilde{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)}$, are the *immaterial* future Scope 1 emissions. They are the remaining future Scope 1 emissions that cannot be predicted through material investments. Thus, $\gamma_{t,s_1(f)} = \bar{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)} + \tilde{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)}$ when $t > T$.

$\tilde{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)}$, is the expected value of future emissions $\hat{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)}$ given what the firm currently announces as its future time t Scope 1 emissions, $\tilde{\gamma}_{a(t),s_1(f)}$, and the firm's characteristics $\rho(f)$. Thus we have, $\tilde{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)} = \mathbb{E}(\hat{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)} | \tilde{\gamma}_{a(t),s_1(f)}, \rho(f))$.

Expectations $\mathbb{E}(\hat{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)} | \tilde{\gamma}_{a(t),s_1(f)}, \rho(f))$ are directly estimated in the survey and shown in Figure 1.C. Using expert knowledge to estimate $\bar{\gamma}_{t,s_1(f)}$ and survey-based estimates of $\tilde{\gamma}$ we can compute $\gamma_{t,s_1(f)}$.

3.3 A company's *intertemporal* carbon impact γ_f

The carbon impact γ_f is the sum of past, current and future carbon impact γ_t with temporal weights $\omega_t, t \in \mathbb{Z}$:

$$\gamma_f = \sum_{t < T} \omega_t \gamma_{t,f} + \omega_T \gamma_{T,f} + \sum_{t > T} \omega_t \gamma_{t,f} \quad (5)$$

The survey asks in Figure 1.B whether present and past weights, ω_t , should be positive or negative. The survey then directly estimates temporal weights, assuming that they are all positive, ranging from 0 to 100. Figure 1.E displays the direct estimates of the present weight ω_T , one past weight and several future weights ω_t .

3.4 A company's *environmental* impact γ_f^e stemming from various pollution types p

The firm f 's environmental impact γ_f^e is the sum of all pollution impacts $\gamma_{p,f}$ in the set of pollution types \mathcal{P} with pollution weights ω_p . Each pollution impact $\gamma_{p,f}$ can be estimated with a methodology similar to the carbon impact γ_f .

$$\gamma_f^e = \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} \omega_p \gamma_{p,f} \quad (6)$$

Weights ω_p are directly estimated in the survey and shown in Figure 1.F.

3.5 A financial asset I 's environmental impact γ_I^e

This paper defines a "venture" $v \in \mathcal{V}$ as a project unit that has its own financial and extra-financial, including environmental accounting. The set \mathcal{V} thus includes a project that could be funded by green financial assets (e.g by green bonds) or a company. The environmental impact of this venture v , γ_v^e is defined using a methodology similar to a firm f 's environmental impact γ_f^e . estimated with a methodology similar to the carbon impact.

The environmental impact γ_I^e of a financial asset $I \in \mathcal{I}$ funding a venture $V \in \mathcal{V}$ is proportional to the venture's environmental impact γ_V^e . It is multiplied by a control weight $\omega_{c(I)}$ which depends on the amount and type of control that the investor J owning the financial asset I holds over the venture. The environmental impact γ_I^e is proportional to the asset's monetary value M_I . It is then divided by the weighted sum of the monetary value of all financial assets funding the venture v :

$$\gamma_I^e = \frac{\omega_{c(I)}M_I}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_v} \omega_{c(i)}M_i} \gamma_V^e \quad (7)$$

The definition of the venture V and the resulting environmental impact γ_V^e is tested in the survey. To define the environmental impact of a bond funding a project with a low environmental impact, should we also partially take into account the environmental impact of the company conducting this project in γ_V^e ? Figure 3A.1 displays the result.

The control weight $\omega_{c(I)}$ first depends on I 's asset class: is it a bond or a stock? $\omega_{c(I)}$ also depends on how much the investor owning the asset I funds or controls the venture V . The survey also investigates the case where the venture is a company, where assets i are stocks, and voting rights are proportional to the share of stocks owned. Investor j owns a stock i . How much does $\omega_{c(I)}$ depend on the share $S_j(i)$ of the stocks owned by j ? How much does it depend on J controlling the company, i.e on having a majority of the shares? To answer both equations, the survey estimates the following equation. It tests whether there is a discontinuity when the share of stocks owned by investor j , $S_j(i)$, equals 50%.

$$\omega_{c(i)} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 S_j(i) + \epsilon_i \quad (8)$$

3.6 A green *portfolio* π 's environmental impact γ_π^e and preferred asset weights

A portfolio π 's environmental impact γ_π^e is the sum of the environmental impact of the N_π financial asset $i \in \mathcal{I}_\pi$ constituting portfolio π :

$$\gamma_\pi^e = \sum_{p \in \mathcal{I}_\pi} \gamma_i^e = \frac{1}{N_\pi} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{I}_\pi} \omega_i \gamma_i^e \quad (9)$$

Portfolio weights ω_i are directly estimated in the survey and shown in Figure 3.B. I study three questions linked to sustainable investment debates, but not included so far in the construction of an asset's purely environmental impact. First, I want to know whether respondents prefer to fund only companies with specific governance structures through green savings products. Second, I investigate how much respondents value transparency. I test whether respondents prefer investing in green saving products that fund activities that they can understand more easily. Should their bank's green assets fund more companies from their region, country or operating in a sector that they understand well? Indeed, one of the most recurring complaints in pre-interviews was the lack of understanding of what savings products in general, not only green products, actually fund. Third, I use that opportunity to extend these questions to include other geographical preferences. Would people prefer green products to fund companies situated outside the EU, from developed or developing countries?

4 Substantial alignment between the most comprehensive frameworks & respondents' preferences

In this whole section, when not explicitly stated otherwise, each weight value refers to the respondents' average of a weight on a 0-100 scale. "All frameworks studied" refers to all frameworks in the Online Appendix ???. In the Online Appendix, for each framework, its acronym and its methodology are described. The methodology was the most recent and openly available one in May 2025.

Figure 1: Preferences over the definition of a company’s environmental impact

Notes Respondents were asked to define a company’s environmental impact. Their bank’s green savings products would only fund companies with a low environmental impact. For the position of the CO_2 emissions in the value chain, the measure of the company’s emissions, the intertemporal carbon impact and the pollution types, respondents chose how much each variable should be accounted for in this environmental impact using a 0-100 slider. For the future emissions, respondents estimate various companies’ future emissions. All these companies had emitted $170tCO_2/year$ until now, but announced they would emit $100tCO_2/year$ in 10 years. For the influence of the company’s profit share in the value chain, respondents compared the environmental impact of a company making a low profit vs. a high profit company. Both companies emit as much CO_2 . Similarly, respondents compared a company with low past & present emissions vs. a company with high past & present emissions. Both companies are certain to emit the same amount of CO_2 next year as they have already undertaken the main material investment.

Respondents value upstream and downstream emissions a little less than Scope 1 emissions

Respondents’ weights for upstream (52) and downstream emissions (51), to compute a carbon impact, are not significantly different. They are both lower than Scope 1 (58) emissions, albeit not much lower.

Such preferences are aligned with frameworks increasingly taking into account Scope 3 rather than a company’s Scope 1 emissions (e.g the evolution of the CDP or the recent CSR). These preferences also justify accounting for a company’s emission along the whole value chain as in Lenzen et al., 2007,

Piñero et al., 2019, rather than only for upstream or only for downstream emissions (Gallego and Lenzen, 2005 or Rodrigues et al., 2010).

The carbon impact should increase with a company’s profit share of its value chain

A company with a lower share of its value chain should have a lower carbon impact than a company with a higher profit share, according to respondents (Figure 1A.2). Both companies are in the same value chain and emit as much.

These preferences are compatible with the fact that more extensive Scope 3 reporting standards are required for bigger companies in practice. It also agrees with methods sharing responsibility for emissions along the firm value chain, according to the value added at each production step as in Lenzen et al., 2007, Piñero et al., 2019.

Offsets, i.e emissions compared to business as usual emissions, have much lower weights than actual emissions

Emissions compared to Business as usual emissions have among the lowest weights (their value equals 52) of all measures related to GHG emissions (Figure 1A.3). They are significantly lower than emission weights (59). Emissions compared to Business as usual emissions correspond to the definition of carbon offsets.

These answers mirror the phased diminution of the importance of carbon offsets in the frameworks studied for carbon emissions (e.g in SBTi, or CDP). However, biodiversity frameworks, that have been developed more recently, currently rely heavily on similar concepts for biodiversity offsets, Mancini et al., 2024.

Contributions to a climate transition scenario have high weights

A company’s emissions compared to its emissions in an ecological transition scenario is the second most highly weighted measure within emission related measures (Figure 3A.3). But this is true only when this scenario is developed by the respondents’ preferred institution (57), not when it is developed by an unknown organization (52).

This is consistent with the debate regarding SBTi’s incentive structure, where most of the association’s revenues are fees from companies they assess and whose emission allocation they set.¹⁰

¹⁰See <https://www.technologyreview.com/2023/05/16/1073064/inside-the-little-known->

Transition scenarios used in environmental corporate accounting should be developed by EU public institutions

French respondents prefer ecological transition scenarios to be developed at the EU rather than the French or international level. They also prefer them to be modelled by the public sector, then by associations that are independent from companies, and then by organizations representing companies' interests (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Preferred institutions in charge of developing the ecological transition scenarios used in corporate environmental reporting

Companies with legally binding alternative governance & incentives have lower estimates of future emissions

A co-determined company, a worker cooperative society, a company with financial incentives for shareholders, or for staff and management related to climate impact, all have low estimates of future emissions in 5 years. These estimates are lower compared to those of a traditional shareholder-governed company (105). A few frameworks such as Carbone 4's Carbon Impact Analysis (CIA), or the Transition Pathway Initiative (TPI) account for the governance and incentive structure when accounting for future emissions.

Respondents were told that each company had emitted $170tCO_2e/year$ so far, but had announced that it would emit $100tCO_2e/year$ in 5 years. This emission reduction is around the minimum projected reduction that could be certified by the SBTi framework. Respondents thus do not believe that a traditional shareholder-governed company will respect future emission announce-

[group-setting-the-corporate-climate-agenda/](#)

ments that could be compatible with SBTi. This is in line with Bjørn et al., 2022 Freiberg et al., 2021. They compare companies' SBTi announcements with their actual emissions a few years later.

A company's high past emissions should increase its carbon impact, even if it reduced its emissions, unlike in the SBTi framework

A company with low past and present emissions should have a lower carbon impact than a company with high past and present emissions. This reflects respondents' preferences when both companies are projected to have similar emissions next year with high certainty. Indeed, it is mentioned that companies already bought all material inputs and infrastructure required for their production.

This contrasts with the SBTi framework, where reducing emissions in the future is prominent. In SBTi, emissions would thus have negative weights according to this paper's quantitative model.

Present and past emissions should weigh less than future emission estimates, but still be accounted for in a cumulative way

Estimates of future emissions in 1, 5, or 10 years have the highest temporal weights (58). Respondents choose these weights, knowing that the estimates of future emissions are those they estimated previously, not those that a company announces. These estimates of future emissions are weighted more than the estimations of future emissions in 2050 (55), present (50) or past emissions from 5 years ago (45). However, present and past emissions should still be counted for in the carbon impact, according to respondents.

Most frameworks studied value future emissions more than present and past ones. In some frameworks such as the transition bonds or green bonds using the Green Bond principles, past and present emissions are not at all accounted for. In contrast, the academic frameworks studied only take into account past or present emissions. Indeed, they choose to rely on actual emissions, not future estimates.

Respondents weigh biodiversity and water usage more than climate impacts, justifying the most recent biodiversity reporting & EU regulations

Water resources and biodiversity should have the highest weights (66) among pollution types, according to respondents (Figure 1E). Their weight should be

significantly higher than for greenhouse gases (60) or other types of pollution, – chemical, nuclear etc. –. (61).

This contrasts starkly with the historical development of the frameworks studied. Indeed, the most comprehensive frameworks, – i.e those that transparently and precisely include all criteria estimated so far in this section–, mostly focus on carbon. Among the frameworks studied, only the EU taxonomy, CSRD, and SFDR regulations, the latest CDP frameworks and the Trucost database simultaneously require reporting carbon, biodiversity, and water impacts.¹¹

Respondents' answers can then be viewed as consistent with the latest evolution of environmental reporting. Indeed, it only recently started to precisely include biodiversity impact and other pollution types. This trend is also present in the latest EU regulations.

¹¹When a company has an impact regarding these pollution types that is material enough.

Figure 3: Preferences over the definition of green financial assets and estimated impact

Notes In Panel A, respondents are asked to define the environmental impact of financial assets. Their bank’s green savings products would only fund assets with a low environmental impact. Respondents compared the environmental impact of two financial assets for each data point. In Panel B, green savings products from the respondent’s bank only fund assets with a low environmental impact. Respondents choose how much their bank’s green savings products should fund each type of company. They use a 0-100 slider. In Panel C, respondents are asked to grade between 0 and 100 how much green savings products contribute to the ecological transition. They do so, with their bank’s current green savings products. At the end of the questionnaire, they do so again. This time, their bank sells them green savings products that follow the criteria they chose.

Project-based green or transition bond accounting should partially take into account the issuing company’s impact

The environmental impact of a bond issued by a renewable company should have a lower carbon impact than that of a bond from an oil company. This is the case when each bond funds a renewable energy project with a similar environmental impact (Figure 3A.1).

This contrasts with the ”venture” defined in green bonds from the Climate Bond Initiative (CBI) or in transition bonds from the International Capital Market Association (ICMA). They only consider the project’s impact in evaluating the asset’s environmental impact.

For stocks, respondents support control-based impact

The regression discontinuity shows that owning a majority of the shares and its corresponding votes significantly increases a stock's impact. However, the share of the stocks that an asset owner possesses is not significantly correlated with a stock's impact.

This is akin to "control-based accounting methods carbon accounting, as in Chancel and Rehm, 2023, López et al., 2014 or Ortiz et al., 2020. These approaches account for the ownership structure of multinational firms by including emissions of domestic and foreign subsidiaries in the footprint of the "controlling" parent company.

Green investment should fund companies with future emission announcements that are credible, thanks to their legally binding alternative governance or incentives

Respondents want green savings products to fund companies with a legally binding alternative governance structure or climate-related financial incentives (Figure 4). The support for a company's inclusion in green savings products is inversely correlated with respondents' estimates of its future emissions (Figure 4 and Figure 1.C).

Figure 4: Support for funding various companies via the respondent's green savings products

Notes Respondents choose whether they would fund these companies via their bank's green savings products. Right before that they were asked to estimate these companies' future emissions (Figure 1C)

Choosing their preferred green criteria through the questionnaire decreases savings products' greenwashing perceptions

After choosing their preferred criteria through the whole questionnaire, respondents rate green savings products that would correspond to their questionnaire choices, if they were offered by their bank. They rate how much these green savings products could help with the ecological transition. They rate them significantly higher (49/100) than their bank's current green savings products (38/100) (see Figure 3.C).

5 Conclusion

This paper develops for the first time a quantitative model that enables comparisons of the criteria involved in the definition an asset's environmental impact, across both corporate reporting standards and academic methods, and whose support for these criteria can be tested.

I find support for environmental reporting's most comprehensive and most

recent approaches, such as the EU CSRD. Respondents support value biodiversity, and water impacts beyond carbon alone. They favor a company's contribution to climate transition scenarios more than carbon offset, if these scenarios are built by public EU institutions. Respondents also support taking into account a company's upstream and downstream emissions, only a little less than Scope 1 emissions.

The results also suggest that a financial asset's environmental impact should combine concepts from corporate reporting as well as from academic carbon accounting. For instance, Value-added carbon accounting could replace Scope 3 to avoid multiple counting of emissions. Future emission pledges could be weighted based on the company's governance structure. Past, present and estimates of future emissions should be weighted but included cumulatively in an asset's environmental impact.

A similar study could be conducted to compare the definitions of a financial asset's social impact. We could then test individual investors' preferences. Indeed, methodologies assessing a company's social impact are less developed than those for environmental impact. Providing more clarity on an asset's social impact might also increase trust in sustainable investment.

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6 Appendix